

LEXICAL AND GRAMMATICAL CLASSIFICATION OF THE SUBJECT IN MODERN ENGLISH

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Abstract. This article examines parts of speech as a way of expressing a topic. In addition, the article presents the main methods of expressing grammatical meanings (synthetic methods of affixation, suppletivism, word formation; analytical methods using task words, prepositions and subordinate clauses, compound and modal verbs), as well as the English sentence word order and intonation are discussed.

Keywords: English language, way of expressing, grammatical meanings, grammatical structure, relation of words.

Parts of speech in modern English - classification of nominative units - words, phrases and sentences - has always been at the center of linguistics. Traditionally, words were divided into parts of speech, although this term contradicts the modern meaning of the term "speech". Essentially, parts of speech are classes of language units, not units of rhea. However, this term is so familiar that it is used by most of the world's linguists. When talking about parts of speech, they usually mean the grammatical classification of lexical units of the language, that is, the allocation in the vocabulary of the language of certain classes of words that differ from other classes in some grammatical feature or features.

When studying this problem, the question arises why the number of parts of speech varies from author to author, why there is no unified classification of parts of speech, for example, in modern English, German, Russian, Uzbek? This situation is obviously explained by the fact that the classification of parts of speech cannot be built on the basis of any one feature, because the vocabulary of a language is a natural system that has been created spontaneously over many millennia, not according to a single plan. Nevertheless, the principles of the basis of classification by parts of speech have been developed in linguistics in sufficient detail. The most common definition is the following: parts of speech are lexical and grammatical sections of words that are grouped on the basis of all the features characteristic of fishing, namely: semantic, morphological and syntactic, when the ability of a word to perform a particular function in a sentence is taken into account.

Significant and service parts of speech

Most domestic scientists divide parts of speech into significant and auxiliary in accordance with the tradition of linguistics. Significant units include units that have a full lexical meaning, that is, those that name objects and concepts (desk, table, love, friendship), actions (bring, kill), signs of objects (big, clever), signs of action (quickly, sharply). Having a full lexical meaning, significant parts of speech occupy one or another syntactic position in a sentence and thus function as certain members of the sentence (subject, predicate, definition, object, circumstance). Among the significant parts of speech today there are: numeral, noun,

adjective, verb, pronoun, adverb and modal words. By grammatical meaning, significant parts of speech are distributed into:

- parts of speech that name objects, phenomena or their signs (noun, adj., num., verb, adverb).
- parts of speech that refer to things as qualities or quantities without naming them (pronouns).
- parts of speech expressing the speaker's attitude to the content of the statement, his feelings and expression of will (modal words, interjections).
- Consider the grammatical properties of some significant parts of speech.

Noun

- The noun in modern English is characterized by the following features:
- The categorial meaning of objectivity. This means that all nouns in the language function in a similar way. Thus, the names of states and properties (activity, freedom, movement) are syntactically equal to the nouns denoting objects (table, folk).
- The presence of a grammatical category of number.
- The grammatical category of number in nouns conveys the grammatical meaning of singularity and plurality, the latter being understood as the number of objects more than one.
- The presence of certain word-forming morphemes typical of the entire class of nouns. Of these, the following are most characteristic: -er, -ist, -ess, -ness, -ion, -ation, -ty, -ment, -ance, -ant.

- Various syntactic functions.
- noun can be a subject, an object, a nominal part of a compound predicate, a definition.

E.g. The child is playing.

Wendy found the money.

Sally became a lady.

David has bought a leather coat.

- The peculiarity of English nouns is that they can act as a prepositive definition in inflected and invariable form.

E.g. a leather coat, a stone wall, John's house.

Adjective

- The adjective as a part of speech is characterized by the following features:
- the grammatical meaning of the property of an object or its attribute, which has a certain conditional stability:
- E.g. a long road, a clever child, a nice boy.
- a certain set of derivational morphemes:
- al, -ial, -ful, -less, -y.
- the adjective name is characterized by only one form of inflection - the degree of comparison.

E.g. big-bigger-the biggest

- Difficult – more difficult – the most difficult

Note that not all adjectives are able to convey the degree of intensity of a particular property. This ability is absent from relative adjectives in their direct meaning.

E.g. the house is more wooden than that one.

The main function of adjectives is to be a definition, both prepositive and postpositive. More characteristic is prepositive functioning.

E.g. a clever boy, a capable student

BUT: secretarygeneral

Another important function of adjectives is the function of the predicative member, that is, the nominal part of the predicate.

E.g. the weather is fine and warm.

Verb

A verb is a part of speech that expresses the grammatical meaning of an action that takes place in time. The grammatical meaning of an action is understood broadly: it is not only an activity in the proper sense of the word, but also a state and an indication that an object exists.

E.g. He wrote a letter.

He sits listening to the music.

A table is a piece of furniture.

The inflectional system of the verb is richer and more diverse than that of other parts of speech. It includes both the synthetic method (addition of formants to the stem) and the analytical forms of tense, aspect, mood, pledge, person, number.

The word-formation structure of the verb is rather poor: affixation is represented by a very small number of suffixes: -ate, -en, -fy, -ize.

Compound verbs formed by conversion are common, as well as verbs formed by reversion, that is, by shortening the final part of nouns.

E.g. broadcast, whitewash - whitewash.

Tiptoe - to walk on tiptoe.

Television → television.

In a sentence, the verb always acts as a predicate. It rarely acts as a definition:

E.g. I would be a student.

Awouldbeststudent.

To correctly translate an English statement, it is not enough to find the Uzbek equivalent of an English word in a dictionary, it is necessary to determine which of the proposed words corresponds to its given use. However, in order to establish the grammatical role, it is necessary to understand the general structure of the statement, since the structure of the phrase in English and Uzbek is different. Therefore, in order to understand the meaning of a statement, it is necessary to identify its grammatical structure. As you know, the grammatical meaning is the meaning of a word, acting as an addition to the lexical meaning of the word and usually expressing various relationships. For example, the relation of words to other words in a phrase or sentence, the relation of the speaker to the speaker, the relation to the person performing the action, etc. The grammatical meaning can be expressed in various ways. In the theory of the English language, there are two ways of expressing grammatical meanings: analytical and synthetic. Each of the ways has a certain set of means of expressing grammatical meanings. Analytical includes service words, order, intonation; and to the synthetic one - affixation, alternation, stress, suppletivism, composition.

In English, stress is fixed and unmovable, although it is not the most typical way of expressing grammatical meaning. This can include several pairs of words, in which the emphasis on the first syllable highlights the noun, and on the second - the verb: 'import

'import' and import 'import', 'object "subject" and object "object", 'encrease "return" and en'crease "increase", 'extract "excerpt, saying", etc. "The expression of mutually opposed grammatical meanings by means of heterogeneous or heterogeneous words is called seppletivism" [1]. In other words, these are forms formed from different roots of a single word. -the largest; beatiful-more beautiful-the most beatiful. Also, seppletivism is typical for paradigms of declension of personal pronouns: I - me, she - her, he - him, we - us, etc. It is believed that the likely way of forming seppletive forms is the loss of opposition between synonymic roots. As a result of this, the forms of opposing grammatical meanings began to form from different roots [1]. The word addition is used only to express derivational grammatical meanings [4]. A compound word is formed as a result of the addition of two or more stems, for example toothache, alarmclock, necktie, necklace. Compound words formed as a result of word formation account for more than one third in the English language. The components that make up a complex word form a single whole and it has one paradigm. Also, a sign of a complex word is the impossibility of modifying its constituent components.

Compound words are classified as follows:

- 1) compound words consisting of simple stems (strawberry - strawberry);
 - 2) compound words consisting of one simple and one derived stem (dressmaker - tailor);
 - 3) compound words, one of the components of which is abbreviations (x-ray - x-ray);
- Compound words, one of the components of which is a complex stem (postmaster-general - minister of post).

Each root morpheme of a compound word can be used as an independent word or as part of other words.

Analytical ways of expressing grammatical meanings.

Functional words are one of the analytical ways of expressing grammatical meanings. They convey a different kind of relationship between significant words. Functional words include prepositions and postpositions, articles, auxiliary verbs, conjunctions, particles, etc.

Unlike the Russian and Uzbek languages, in the English language there are not only prepositions, but also postpositions. They show relationships between words in a sentence. The very definition comes from the name: prepositions are placed before nouns, pronouns or other words, precede something; postpositions are after verbs and give the verb a different meaning or complement the existing one. For example, write off - cancel, write up - describe in detail, to write somebody up for - recommend anyone (kypc treatment). In English, postpositions are often used, and in the dictionary it is necessary to search for a verb with a postposition, otherwise its meaning can be misunderstood. Prepositions help indicate the correct relationship between words in a sentence. Sentences can be divided into simple, consisting of one syllable (to, in, at, by, with), complex, consisting of two syllables or even separate elements (into, inside, before, behind, upon), and compound, representing a combination significant part of speech with a simple preposition, having a general meaning (as far as, as for, because of, in front of). Suggestions can be: spatial, temporal, causal, target, etc. Prepositions of place indicate position in space and direction, they are the most commonly used prepositions: in, at, on, by, next, to, beside, under, below, over, above, across, though, into, towards, onto, from. Time prepositions can indicate the exact time, period, start and end time of the action: on, in, at, during, since, for, over, before, to, till, until, by. In addition to the meaning of place and time, prepositions can have more abstract meanings,

they can indicate the purpose, reason, area of activity, occupation, etc.: due to, because of, despite, like, by, but, apart from, etc.

In this article, the main ways of expressing grammatical meanings in English were considered and analyzed. All considered methods are divided into two types: synthetic and analytical. Where grammatical ways represent the expression of grammatical meaning within a triword, they are called synthetic. In turn, the expression of grammatical meaning outside the word is handled by analytical methods. The English language uses mainly the latest ways, so we can talk about its analytical structure.

To summarize the above about grammatical meanings: the grammatical meaning represents a generalized reflection of the object reality. The purpose of this work was to study the ways of expressing grammatical meaning in English. From the theoretical point of view, the main ways of expressing the grammatical meaning are described and examples are given.

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